

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Keynote of the case letter

The occurrence in international PhD school is a PhD tragedy in Australian PhD school. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist has faced life-threatening conspiracy and PhD conspiracy in Australian PhD School at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia since 2021-2022. Therefore, Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of the United Nations (UN) for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding in international PhD school. UN should be liable to take necessary action against international criminals. Accordingly, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist has scholarly inventions and long-term investment from 2021-2022. Under the action and support of the UN,

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every national and international political leader is being requested to extend their ethical beauty to take necessary action against international criminals. Let's shout and shout for a 'criminal free' world which may enhance the global survival capability, global peace, peace in PhD school, and lifetime of the peoples.

Proposal of legal act and/or outcome of the case study and crime analysis

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is proposing a victim-friendly penalty for every government.

- 1. Every victim will get 80% of the total approved penalty unit for the time investment, crime reporting, crime analysis support, and compensation.*
- 2. Every legal practitioner will get 10% of the total approved penalty unit for the time investment, reporting and crime analysis.*
- 3. Every government will get 10% of the total approved penalty unit for the administrative charge and magistracy costs.*
- 4. Every crime offender will be liable to pay 100% of the total approved penalty unit for the support of crime analysis.*

Keywords

Legal support, legal stipend, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, United Nations

Date: 19 January 2025

Mr. António Guterres
Secretary-General, United Nations
Office of Secretary-General, United Nations
United Nations Secretariat Building, 405 East 42nd Street,
New York, NY, 10017, USA.

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Dear Secretary-General,

Your excellency for the action and support for the peace of human being.

Your honour to ensure global legal rights in international court in international PhD school.

I, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, am a Bangladeshi national. I have been an Australian PhD researcher since 2020 funded by Australian government RTP stipend scholarship. My full biodata is being attached and submitted here to the office of Secretary-General, United Nations (UN).

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14217868>

I would like to notify you that I faced a life-threatening conspiracy, PhD tragedy, and PhD conspiracy in Australian PhD School at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. I can not continue with legal proceedings due to the financial crisis due to lack of financial ability, capability, and strength when I am a full-time PhD researcher when I have no income support. I have been struggling and struggling from 2021-2022. After writing few notices, I can not convince the relevant authorities of the Australian government. I have not been getting free of cost legal support of Australian government and/or relevant authorities since 2022. I should have a legal right to get free of cost legal support if I am a legal unit of human being. I also asked for free of cost protection support, life-time safety support, life-time income support or living allowance support under the parallel action and support of Australian government and RMIT University. Accordingly, I proposed to the government of Australia to pay 230,72,50,000 AUD (two hundred thirty crore seventy-two lakh and fifty thousand Australian dollar) for my 'PhD compensation award' for my scholarly convincing to the whole Australian government. My Australian salary has been suspended since 6 July 2022 when I noticed my life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school under the Australian quality of research framework.

Australian PhD school officially taught or trained me, “Every accidental issue or life-threatening issue or suspicious issue should report to the top management and/or relevant management of PhD school.” Every complaint of a PhD category researcher should be assessed under the way of victim-friendly. Every government should be victim-friendly. Every university should be victim-friendly. Every organization should be victim-friendly. Every person should be victim-friendly. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye not only tried to kill or harass my dream of Australian PhD schooling, but Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye continued and continued crime conspiracy of hidden life-threatening in Australian PhD school under the hidden connection and/or techniques with the people in Bangladesh and Australia. Without lawful reason, criminal conspiracy against a victim is an additional challenge in PhD school. Criminal conspiracy in international PhD school is a symptom of violation of international human rights. Criminal conspiracy should be banned in Australian PhD school. Under the support of the UN; killing conspiracy in Australian PhD school should be investigated and banned immediately. Therefore, nobody should have the right to kill a PhD researcher. Therefore, nobody should make hidden plans to kill a PhD researcher. Let’s eliminate the criminal conspiracy from the Australian PhD school. May I seek your attention and action under the funding of the UN. Practically, it is so tough to reimburse a victim. So, let’s shout and shout for a ‘criminal free’ PhD school. So, let’s shout and shout for a ‘criminal free’ world.

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Accordingly, I have notified to Mr. Anothony Albanese, Prime minister of Australia since 2nd December 2023. I have also notified to minister of Australian home affairs, minister of Australian education department, minister of Australian foreign affairs, Australian high court, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government, Vice Chancellor of RMIT University, and other relevant authorities of Bangladesh and Australian government since 2021-2022. I also submitted a printed letter to the office of Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President of Bangladesh government; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, chief advisor of Bangladesh government on 7 November 2024 (electronic letter) and 9 November 2024 (printed letter by Sundarban courier service private ltd.) and relevant authorities of Bangladesh government. I have also missed PhD schooling support since 6 July 2022 under the continuous life-threatening and parallel harassment of official PhD schooling at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Nobody should cease my legal right of PhD schooling under the life-threatening conspiracy and criminal conspiracy. No professor should cease my legal right to PhD schooling under the life-threatening conspiracy and criminal conspiracy. If a university professor was also a PhD researcher, and nobody ceased his PhD schooling. The situation in PhD school is directly hampering the global principle of education. The situation in PhD school is directly demotivating the young PhD researchers who have life-long investments who have life-long dreams in the peace of global survival and the global principle of quality education. I, applicant should have a global humanitarian right to raise my legal voice in front of international judicial board when I have been a victim from 2021-2022.

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Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

It should not be my non-paid duty to notify Australian government from 2021-2022. This is not my official duty to write a letter to the office of the Secretary-General of the UN. But the situation is pulling me to the UN Secretary-General if there is an existing ethical beauty for the support of international category victims. Unfortunately, by born, I am not financially solvent to face any

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international criminal to face any international court. Unfortunately, I asked for safety against a professor in PhD school but I got PhD suspension instead of ensuring safety in Australia and Bangladesh. These are the issues of global headache for global survival in an international community when international criminals are technologically, financially, and illegally solvent. Due to the submission of a protest letter to the Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; my PhD salary or PhD scholarship has been dishonestly suspended since 6 July 2022. Unfortunately, I highlighted against a professor at RMIT University. A PhD researcher should have a right to ask every safety support to the Vice Chancellor against a criminal in PhD school. A PhD researcher should have a right to ask every safety support to the Vice Chancellor as per Australian quality of research framework. A victim got PhD suspension but the professor continued and continued his repeated criminal conspiracy under the administrative umbrella of RMIT University. It was not the ethical beauty in Australian PhD school. The life-threatening conspiracy was being executed in Australian PhD school. Possibly, the life-threatening conspiracy was also extended in Bangladesh when I moved from Australia to Bangladesh due to self-protection of criminal conspiracy in Australian PhD school at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University. I should have the legal right to ask for punishment against a dishonest professor who has a high level of expertise in criminal conspiracy in an Australian PhD school who is a habituated criminal or professional criminal who is the international enemy of professor community. Since 6 July 2022, I have missed PhD schooling and the official guidance of my PhD professors under the illegal harassment in an international PhD school. Nobody should stop my PhD schooling unethically and fraudulently if I am a legal part of human being. Still, I have been practicing full-time PhD from 2019-2020. Still, I have been writing a criminal conspiracy in an Australian PhD school from 2021-2022. My PhD contributions in the Australian PhD school are being noted, coalesced, attached and submitted here for the assessment of the UN authorized committee under the international PhD awarding protocol in the Australian PhD school. Presently and possibly, this is also necessary to initiate an international PhD awarding protocol under the administration of the UN if every PhD researcher needs to satisfy the international researcher and/or professor community.

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Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282063>

My PhD harassments in Australian PhD school are being noted, coalesced, attached, and presented here for the UN committee assessment and/or pre-trial assessment (attached a filled form of interview request) of international criminal court.

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223162>

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It is also being mentioned that Australian government has no legal insurance and/or legal stipend policy and/or legal support policy for international PhD scholars. Every scholar is not financially solvent. Australian home affairs didn't ask me any bank statement to admit me in Australian PhD school to issue an Australian student VISA funded by Australian government RTP stipend scholarship. An appointed PhD scholar should not be a self-funded PhD researcher under the life-threatening conspiracy, criminal conspiracy, and PhD conspiracy. Every legal proceeding is expensive in Australia. Moreover, if the criminal is international in an international PhD school, the UN should also be responsible to ensure the legal fund to ensure the criminal free PhD schooling to ensure victim support against the international criminal in Australian PhD school. UN action and support should be applicable to ensure victim support in Australian PhD school.

Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>

Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

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Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Extension support of Australian student VISA was also being successfully denied by the Australian home affairs. If I am a PhD student, if I am a PhD researcher, if I am a victim, if I need to go to Australian court, Australian government should be liable to approve an Australian student VISA. So, what was the official duty of Australian home affairs or education department to continue international PhD service in Australian PhD school under the active government of Australia. On 3rd January 2025, I telephoned the department of the global service centre of Australian Home Affairs on +612 6196 0196 who advised me to apply for Australian tourist VISA under the circumstances of applicant. The global service team told me, “You just need a VISA, you can not enter Australia without VISA, so you can apply for the tourist VISA.” I am not a tourist in Australia, I am a PhD researcher in Australia when I am facing a critical conspiracy in Australian PhD school. Moreover, who will take the responsibilities of my living and fooding expenses for court processing in Australia? Moreover, I also need fund to submit printed copy of the brief history of the criminal conspiracy in Australian PhD school. There are no rules of Australian government to overcome the critical issues of a victim when victim is an international when victim is a Bangladeshi citizen when victim is a PhD scholar. Criminal/criminals is/are doing their professional duty successfully, but victim can not continue his official and professional duty in PhD school. What is the global respect to a PhD scholar? I am being confused and confused. I am a long-term sufferer and sufferer. How can I raise my written voice in Australian court? Who should be responsible? I would like to hear from the office Secretary-General of the UN if we are respecting international community under the principle of global surviving. I also asked for safety in Bangladesh and Australia against international criminal and/or Australian criminal. These are the symptom of international PhD trapping. Every PhD trapping or PhD harassment should be an official crime. International support team and/or UN should have a legal way to solve such type of critical issues in a friendly way in a victim-friendly way. There is huge scope of research and

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development of international PhD awarding policy. UN should have a logical scope for legal funding or legal-aid support to solve the international crime to minimize the international crime in Australian PhD school if Bangladesh and Australia are the active member of the UN. All criminal conspiracies are also being regularly notified and informed to the relevant authorities of Bangladesh government and Australian government. I have also been notified to the relevant national and international community under the self-funding since 2022. All criminal conspiracies are also sincerely, obediently, and briefly notified to the Prime Minister of Australia and Prime Minister/Chief advisor of Bangladesh for their relevant action and support for their chief executive support for their honest support for their legal support for their kind attention for their sincere action against international criminal conspiracies in Australian PhD school. But I am not a country, but I am not a society, but I am not an office, but I am not a community, but I am not a political community in Bangladesh & Australia, but I am not a university, but I am a single man since 6 July 2022 when I am writing and writing when I am convincing and convincing when I am begging and begging when I am requesting and requesting when I am obedient and obedient on behalf of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; self-funded by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; self-invested by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; self-supervised by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, self-administered by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist. I should get every compensation of my full-time official duty hours under the global compliance support of UN under the global assessment support of UN under the global ethical beauty of UN. Hence, I would like to see the ethical beauty UN. Hence, I would like to show the ethical beauty of UN to the global community to the professor community to the researcher community to the scientist community to the student community.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14498859>

UN should give me a value of my long-term self-investment in education by ensuring the life-time safety support under the protection support against Australian criminal and/or professional criminal and/or criminal community in Australia.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

"Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>

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I also asked support to UN, I also tried to convince UN if I can get any funding of UN to continue my one-dimensional PhD research and/or scientist practices for the global excellency. But I faced criminal conspiracy in the name of UN communications in the name of scientist support in the name of UN support. UN should make a committee to eliminate the international criminals if there is criminal conspiracy in the name of UN scam.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Under the critical circumstances, I should have a way to claim international court and/or Australian court under the funding support and/or legal support and safety support of UN and/or Australian government. I saw the relevant funding support on the website of the UN. Could you please let me know that what should I do to get legal support of international court and/or Australian court? Could you please let me know that what should I do to get legal stipend of UN? Could you please let me know that what should I do for the life-time protection and income support against criminal conspiracy in Australian PhD school?

May I seek international safety to the Secretary-General of the UN under the international protection against international criminal and/or criminal community, possibly criminals are more active in Bangladesh and Australia.

***Your Honour, Please Pardon me
Best Regards for your excellency for the peace of mankind***

19 January 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

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If Necessary, Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023ao; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Samanta et al., 2016) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (**Hossain, 2023ah, 2023al, 2023bh, 2023cg, 2023ch**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bv, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf,

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2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024x, 2024y; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024z)

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For showing my honour, for the excellency of PhD schooling and human being all over the world; may I am also forward (randomly sequenced) a copy of this letter for their excellency

Mr. Philemon Yang

President of the General Assembly, United Nations

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

References

- Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>
- Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01.
<http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>
- Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>
- Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 3(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 4(4).

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effect-of-Variation-in-Different-Mechanical-Setting-Hossain/9402f52697c08f2b6104abb07e1f4f414aa3f332>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650>

Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online)*, USA.

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>;

<https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>

Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azadirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21790.51524>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>

Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>; https://pure.hw.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/92968499/Modern_Technology_versus_Rapid_Economical_Growth....pdf; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245107>

Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237842>

Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>

Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>

Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN-978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>

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Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Principle of garments production, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh.* Rupok Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>

Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304637>

Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments* (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28804.50568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311367>

Hossain, M. A. (2018). *Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles* (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17899.31521>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311345>

Hossain, M. A. (2019a). Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>; <http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>

Hossain, M. A. (2019b). Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>

Hossain, M. A. (2019c). Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn. *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2). <https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002>;
https://sarpublishation.com/media/articles/SARJET_12_43-49_c.pdf

Hossain, M. A. (2019d). Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850320>

- Hossain, M. A. (2020). My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <http://pubs.sciepub.com/materials/9/1/3/>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination* (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.101537>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370. <https://publications.drdo.gov.in/ojs/index.php/dsj/article/view/17731/7785>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background* (Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286740>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics. *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia*. <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49095>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7944616>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223162>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240342>

Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238071>

Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,

- Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238806>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8232618>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239492>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240371>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240383>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240507>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>
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Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>

Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>

Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240703>

Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240796>

Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240984>

Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>

Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar,

- Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241105>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245088>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241291>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233503>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233914>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka,*

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286913>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). *Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023; Valencia, Spain, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023; Rome, Italy, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

Hossain, M. A. (2023al). *Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297554>

Hossain, M. A. (2023am). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>

Hossain, M. A. (2023an). *Conference Presentation on "Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology"; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and*

- Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.22407>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117340>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). *Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747451>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023at). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2025, designated for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862986>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering.* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240852>
 Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970344>

Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970310>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970241>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

Hossain, M. A. (2023be). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bh). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298582>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311145>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University;* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bq). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286771>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023br). Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318727>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

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engranowar06@gmail.com

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>

Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182709>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cb).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (enr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cd). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions. *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia* (enr.anowar@yahoo.com). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02)*.

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of "Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist" on "Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds"* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

- Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14498859>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'*.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
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engranowar06@gmail.com

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245079>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. K. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-cost-minimization-process-of-heat-and-energy-for-Hossain-Samanta/145246a45b40a7ef33c3e37cc99083f91f6555fa>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science &*

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Engineering, 8(5), 1-5. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Non-toxic-Coloration-of-Cotton-Fabric-using-and-Hossain-Samanta/76a9a8128bc038db760f2b93328e4eefeb2ae4d1>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>

Samanta, A. K., Hossain, A., Bagchi, A., & Bhattacharya, K. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*, 2(4), 25-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

To request an interview with an ICC official, please fill out this form and return it to publicaffairs.unit@icc-cpi.int

Please submit separate forms for each person you wish to interview.

To request an interview with members of the Office of the Prosecutor, please fill out this form and return it to otpnewsdesk@icc-cpi.int

Please submit separate forms for each person you wish to interview.

Interview request

Contact details

- Your full name: Md. Anowar Hossain
Name & Title: Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist
- Organization: RMIT University
- Type of organization: University or research institute
- Country: Australia
- Phone number: +8801788396264
- E-mail address: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
- Physical address Proposed

Permanent Residence (PR) By Birth and/or Present Address in Bangladesh

Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia; Nationality, National ID, Passport and Birth Registration Number: Bangladeshi (by birth), 19862692620993890, A15988852 (Present)/ EE0444946/AF3831770 (previous), 003236.

Official Address

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25
 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT
 University, Melbourne, Vic-3056, The
 Commonwealth of Australia.

Interview date (s):

Any suitable Bangladeshi time and date under request with e-mail address: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; mobile: +8801788396264

ICC personnel you wish to interview (if known):

Type of interview you are requesting:

- Written ✓
- telephone
- in person
- in person, recorded
- in person, filmed Duration of

Proposed interview:

Detailed description of your project's intended content:

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;

General topic of the interview:

Free of cost legal support (travel, living, fooding, safety, lawyers, monthly salary allowance & compensation, etc.) of applicant, Nobel Nominee

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

Specific interview questions:

May I seek free of cost legal support in international court in international PhD school under the following circumstances

Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

PhD Research and outcomes

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282063>

PhD Harassments

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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engranowar06@gmail.com

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223162>

PhD supervisors in Australian PhD school

Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist
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Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist
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¹ PhD candidates and other academic researchers are kindly requested to also provide contact information for their research supervisor and an abstract of their research project.

Evidence of e-mail communications

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

Yahoo/Sent

Page | 50

Anowar Hossain

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au, robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au, robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com, contact.centre@education.gov.au, vc@rmit.edu.au, brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au, ea.vc@rmit.edu.au, jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au, nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au, vso@dfat.gov.au, secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd, press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd, ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd, akmmonirul31@gmail.com, majumderali1950@gmail.com, musfiquldu33@gmail.com, psecy@cao.gov.bd, secretary@cao.gov.bd, seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd, lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd, sultanpmo1974@gmail.com, ddresearch@cao.gov.bd, jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd, infoservice@humanrights.gov.au, consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, registrar@du.ac.bd, publicaffairs.unit@icc-cpi.int, otpnewsdesk@icc-cpi.int, liaisonofficeny@icc-cpi.int, Security@icc-cpi.int, Procurement@icc-cpi.int, asp@icc-cpi.int, tgchague@tgchambers.com, ICCVisits@icc-cpi.int, information@icj-cij.org, cdldb21@gmail.com, customer@bl.uk, library@icj-cij.org, repository@rmit.edu.au, Registry@hcourt.gov.au, fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd, secretary@ugc.gov.bd, syrawarn@gmail.com, nazmul@ugc.gov.bd, director_research@ugc.gov.bd, ferdousugc@gmail.com, chairman@ugc.gov.bd, mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd, mustafizugc@gmail.com, pschairman@ugc.gov.bd, vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd, registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd, s.islam05@gmail.com, saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd, ijtskg40@gmail.com, sadhan53@yahoo.co.in, ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au, consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au, fs@mofa.gov.bd, dirfso@mofa.gov.bd, ssa@mofa.gov.bd, aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd, dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd, dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd, asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd, ftm@nhrc.org.bd, chairman@nhrc.org.bd, secretary@nhrc.org.bd, liptonbjs@gmail.com, letters@theaustralian.com.au, victoria@theaustralian.com.au, wa@theaustralian.com.au, act@theaustralian.com.au, dunning@callinanchambers.com.au, contact@austbar.asn.au, media@austbar.asn.au, scba.bd@gmail.com, info@barindia.in, barindia1959@gmail.com, service@americanbar.org, ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk, press@barcouncil.org.uk, info.eseprobangkok@amnesty.org, contactus@amnesty.org, vc@butex.edu.bd, registrar@butex.edu.bd, head@dce.butex.edu.bd, butexdce@gmail.com, andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au, scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au, sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au, xin.wa

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Cc:customer@bl.uk

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:35 PM

Dear Nobel
winner/Chairman/Sir/Madam/Professor/Dr./Scientist/President
/Chief advisor/lawyer/Minister/Vice Chancellor/High
Commissioner/Secretary/Director/Editor,

Your excellency for the peace of mankind.

May I attach a link and pdf file of a cc letter.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

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Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

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BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]

Opened - [CC1641189] - [Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with le ETKN:025000036800

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

Yahoo/Inbox

Education - Contact Centre

Page | 54

From: contact.centre@education.gov.au

To: Anowar Hossain

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:41 PM

Hi,

Thank you for contacting the Departmental Contact Centre team.

We endeavour to respond to your email as soon as possible.

Please note, information can also be obtained on the Department's website.

For any future correspondence about this enquiry, please quote case reference number [CC1641189].

Show original message

Departmental Contact Centre
Australian Government Department of Education
Phone: 1300 363 079 | Email: contact.centre@education.gov.au

www.education.gov.au

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Yahoo/Inbox

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Grants

From: grants@vla.vic.gov.au

To: Anowar Hossain

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Thank you for contacting Victoria Legal Aid Grants and Quality Assurance. From Monday 23 December until Friday 3 January, we will be operating with a skeleton staff and you may experience some delays in responses to your enquiry. Your enquiry is important to us and we appreciate your patience during this time. Thank you

Appreciate your assistance with this request
Thank you

Victoria Legal Aid's website makes it easier for all Victorians to find services and information to help with their legal problem. Visit www.legalaid.vic.gov.au.

AHRC Make a Complaint Form

Yahoo/Inbox

Australian Human Rights Commission

From: noreply@humanrights.gov.au

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:50 PM

**Australian
Human Rights
Commission**

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.

Complaint

- **Your complaint has been sent!**

Thank you for submitting the complaint form to the Australian Human Rights Commission (the Commission).

If you do not receive contact from the Commission within the next 7 days, please contact the Commission on 1300 656 419 (Monday to Friday 10.00am to 4.00pm Sydney time) or by email at infoservice@humanrights.gov.au to confirm receipt.

INTERPOL General Secretariat, Date 1 February 2025

You can get in touch with INTERPOL using the form below. Your message will be forwarded to the appropriate department but please note that we are unable to respond to all queries.

Thank you for your feedback.

Seeking a case filing support under the category of international student at RMIT University, Australia

Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: information@icj-cij.org

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Mon, Feb 10 at 6:38 PM

Dear Registrar,

Can I proceed a case filing under the category of international student at RMIT University, Australia? I notified a copy of the letter for your assessment and consideration.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Could you please let me know online or offline case filing process at international court?

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

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Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 19 January 2025.